

National assessment on the status, trends and impacts of marine non-indigenous species for the European Union marine strategy framework directive

Okko Outinen^{a,*}, Tarja Katajisto^a, Henrik Nygård^a, Riikka Puntila-Dodd^{a,b}, Maiju Lehtiniemi^a

^a Marine and Freshwater Solutions, Finnish Environment Institute, Latokartanonkaari 11, 00790 Helsinki, Finland

^b Environmental and Marine Biology, Åbo Akademi University, Henrikinkatu 2, FI-20500 Turku, Finland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Marine Strategy Framework Directive
Environmental indicators
Biodiversity
Invasive Alien Species
Monitoring

ABSTRACT

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) of the European Union aims to enhance the protection of marine ecosystems by assessing Good Environmental Status using several descriptors. Descriptor 2 of the MSFD states that the status of marine non-indigenous species (NIS) should be assessed using specified criteria regarding newly introduced NIS, abundance, and spatial distribution of established NIS, as well as proportions of native species groups adversely altered due to NIS. The current study presents a national NIS indicator assessment for the six sub-basins associated with the Finnish marine waters. The study additionally aimed to develop a methodology to assess changes in native species communities over time. A new biodiversity index was created for this purpose by combining the Gini-Simpson index, and species and phyla richness into a Community Biodiversity Index (CBI). CBI was calculated to measure changes in biodiversity within the soft-bottom benthic communities of the study area, and correlation analyses were conducted between the index scores and NIS proportion. Overall, 34 NIS have been recorded from the Finnish marine waters by 2022, and more than half of them have arrived since 1992. Spatial distribution of three established non-indigenous taxa (*Marenzelleria* spp., *Cercopagis pengoi* and *Neogobius melanostomus*) has expanded during the latest assessment periods and nowadays cover most of the national marine waters. Meanwhile, abundance of *Marenzelleria* spp. in benthic communities has increased heavily in most sub-basins. The study outcomes indicated that NIS proportion correlated significantly with the CBI within the soft-bottom benthic communities. This correlation was significantly negative for the samples with a higher NIS proportion than the median, suggesting that when NIS became more dominant, biodiversity of the communities decreased. The current study provides an applicable method to evaluate changes in biodiversity for various species groups, and how to link them to changes in the distribution and abundance of established NIS. It can be concluded that the national biological monitoring program has severe temporal and spatial gaps, as the national monitoring data enabled the assessment on native species groups, adversely altered due to NIS to be completed only for one species group, soft-bottom macrozoobenthos. Most importantly, the study emphasised the crucial need for management actions to prevent further NIS introductions.

1. Introduction

The intensification of globalisation has applied various pressures towards the marine environment since the beginning of the industrialised era, and the increase of global seaborne trade alone has more than quadrupled in the last 50 years from 2,6 to over 11 billion tons (UNCTAD, 2021). This trajectory has further increased pressures on marine environment and biodiversity. One major source of pressure, the spread of aquatic non-indigenous species (NIS), is an unintentional by-

product of international shipping (Ruiz et al., 1997).

Several international and regional policies have been developed and adopted in the late 20th and early 21st centuries to tackle the spread of NIS, and essentially restore and sustain the ecosystems and biological functions within the marine environment (Ojaveer et al., 2014; Lehtiniemi et al., 2015; Ojaveer et al., 2018). Within the context of the European Union (EU), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the Biodiversity Strategy aim to enhance the protection of marine ecosystems. The MSFD sets out 11 descriptors with the goal of reaching

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: okko.outinen@syke.fi (O. Outinen).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111593>

Received 23 August 2023; Received in revised form 29 December 2023; Accepted 12 January 2024

Available online 20 January 2024

1470-160X/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Good Environmental Status (GES), which is assessed and reviewed in six-year periods (EC, 2008, 2011, 2020; Tsiamis et al., 2021). Further, EU Commission decision 2017/848 provided updated criteria and methodological standards to assess GES under each descriptor (EC, 2017). More specifically, descriptor 2 (D2) states that NIS introduced by human activities should not adversely alter ecosystems. D2 includes one primary criterion (D2C1) and two secondary criteria (D2C2 and D2C3) with links to descriptors D1 (Biodiversity) and D6 (Sea-floor integrity) of the MSFD, as well as methodological standards to assess these criteria (Table 1).

EU has encouraged its Member States to establish a threshold value for the primary criterion D2C1 to define whether sea areas are in GES, as well as assess secondary criteria D2C2 and D2C3 through regional or subregional cooperation (EC, 2017). Baltic Sea is one of the five marine regions under EU jurisdiction (EC, 2008). Assessment of the primary criterion D2C1 on behalf of the Baltic Sea countries is conducted and reported through the Contracting Parties of the Helsinki Convention (Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission, HELCOM). The first Baltic Sea NIS core indicator assessment was conducted for 2011–2016 (HELCOM, 2018), whereas the latest assessment addressed the period of 2016–2021 (HELCOM, 2023a). Concerning D2C1, Contracting Parties of HELCOM have agreed that no new NIS should be introduced to the Baltic Sea through human activities during each six-year assessment period to reach GES (Olenin et al., 2016; HELCOM, 2018). HELCOM has acknowledged that due to insufficient monitoring resources, there are inconsistencies in the availability of information and knowledge across the sub-basins of the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2018). Therefore, the assessment concerns only new species to the entire Baltic Sea, and not secondarily spread species into new areas within the Baltic Sea.

However, there are no HELCOM indicators for the secondary criteria D2C2 and D2C3. The present guidance document for the assessment of EU MSFD D2 (Tsiamis et al., 2021) has stated that these secondary criteria may be assessed using the Biopollution level (BPL) index (Olenin et al., 2007), or the Cumulative Impacts of invasive Alien species (CIMPAL) model on marine ecosystems (Katsanevakis et al., 2016). The BPL index provides an assessment concept on how to address D2C2 and D2C3 in relation to temporal and spatial changes in NIS distribution, abundance, as well as impacts on native species communities, habitats and ecosystems (Olenin et al., 2007). The index has divided distribution

Table 1

Assessment criteria and methodological standards for EU MSFD D2 (EC, 2017). *Established NIS in this context refer to those NIS that were known to be present in the area during the previous assessment period and therefore are not new in the following assessment period.

Criterion	Methodological standards
<p>Primary criterion D2C1:</p> <p>The number of newly introduced NIS via human activities per an assessment period of six years is minimised and where possible reduced to zero.</p>	<p>Scale of assessment – Subdivisions of the MSFD region or subregion. Assessment can be divided by national boundaries wherever needed.</p> <p>Use of criteria – The extent to which GES has been achieved shall be expressed for each area assessed as follows: The number of NIS newly introduced via human activity within the 6-year assessment period (list of those species).</p>
<p>Secondary criterion D2C2:</p> <p>Abundance and spatial distribution of established NIS*, particularly of invasive species with adverse impacts on particular species groups or broad habitat types.</p>	<p>Scale of assessment – Reference should be made to species groups or broad habitat types described under Descriptors 1 and 6.</p> <p>Use of criteria – D2C2 shall be expressed for each established NIS, and it should contribute to the D2C3 assessment.</p>
<p>Secondary criterion D2C3:</p> <p>Proportion of a species group or spatial extent of the broad habitat type adversely altered due to NIS, particularly invasive NIS.</p>	<p>D2C3 shall provide the proportion of species group and extent of broad habitat type adversely altered by NIS, and thus contribute to assessments under Descriptors 1 and 6.</p>

of NIS into four categories between ‘local’ and ‘all localities’, as well as abundance of NIS to three categories from ‘low’ to ‘high’. Further, the assessment concept provides relatively similar ranking categories regarding NIS impacts on native species communities, habitats and ecosystem functioning, and eventually combines the scores based on these categories into five biopollution levels (0 – No biopollution to 4 – Massive biopollution), and these levels should be assessed for each NIS separately. The BPL index has been previously assessed for nine sub-regions of the Baltic Sea (Zaiko et al., 2011).

The CIMPAL index provides an assessment framework, where a cumulative impact score is mapped for each grid cell of the study area. This score is based on presence or abundance of NIS that are known to have adverse impacts, habitat extent and distribution of the area, and impact weight for each NIS regarding the habitats present (Katsanevakis et al., 2016). The CIMPAL index methodology categorises the impact weight using the strength of evidence of adverse effects and magnitude of impact, but the CIMPAL index score is assessed for a grid cell, and it includes simultaneously all NIS in the area with known impacts (Katsanevakis et al., 2016). Furthermore, more recent national NIS assessments, such as Staehr et al. (2020) and Jensen et al. (2023) have utilised other assessment approaches that include the potential impact of other environmental factors on species communities, as well as discussed the use of expert evaluations with respect to NIS impact assessments. While the MSFD D2 guidance document reports that the BPL and CIMPAL indices may be used for D2C2 and D2C3 assessments, it equally reflects the concerns of the NIS experts of EU Member States that monitoring data are often lacking for several species groups to conduct these assessments (Ojaveer et al., 2021; Tsiamis et al., 2021).

There have been several attempts to assess the biological impacts of marine NIS in EU waters (Olenin et al., 2007; Zaiko et al., 2011; Katsanevakis et al., 2016; Staehr et al., 2020; Ojaveer et al., 2021). However, a unified assessment framework that evaluates the impacts of NIS on native biota is still clearly lacking. Furthermore, lack of unified methodology to assess these secondary criteria will inevitably result in inadequate reporting on national and regional levels. The purpose of the present study was to conduct a national indicator assessment for the Finnish marine waters according to MSFD D2 primary criterion D2C1. In addition, the current study aimed at evaluating secondary criteria D2C2 and D2C3. Finally, further attention was drawn to the development of an assessment methodology on how to measure changes in native species communities over time.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area included the Finnish exclusive economic zone waters, which are divided into the Gulf of Finland (GoF), Northern Baltic Proper (NBP), Åland Sea (AS, including the coastal Archipelago Sea), Bothnian Sea (BS), the Quark (Q) and Bothnian Bay (BB) according to HELCOM level 2 sub-basin delineation (HELCOM, 2022) (Appendix A). The spatial coverage of certain national open sea monitoring stations extends to neighbouring waters of Estonia, Russian Federation and Sweden, and NIS recorded from these stations are included in the D2C2 distribution analyses.

Baltic Sea is commonly characterised as an enclosed regional sea with relatively strong latitudinal gradients regarding salinity, water temperatures and seasonality (Sjöqvist et al., 2015; HELCOM, 2018). Baltic Sea region is only moderately connected to the more saline North Sea through the narrow and shallow straits between Denmark and Sweden, and the freshwater input from numerous river catchments is notable, especially in the Northern Baltic Sea. Further, the Baltic Sea can be considered as a sink to pollutants and nutrients, where these pressures accumulate and magnify over time due to relatively poor natural connectivity within the Sea region (Sjöqvist et al., 2015). These characteristics are also the primary reason why the regional biodiversity in

the study area is relatively species poor. More importantly, such environmental and seasonal conditions can prevent the establishment of several oceanic NIS that require high salinities e.g., for reproduction, even though they may be preferable to euryhaline and oligohaline NIS (Holopainen et al., 2016).

2.2. Monitoring stations and methods

NIS records in the Finnish marine waters rely on national biological monitoring, statutory monitoring programmes, various research projects and citizen science observations. The biological monitoring program can be divided into monitoring of soft-bottom macrozoobenthos, coastal hard-bottom macrophyte and mussel communities, fishes, as well as zooplankton and phytoplankton communities (Table 2) (HELCOM, 2017; Syke, 2020). Coastal and open sea monitoring data were assessed separately in this study (Table 2) due to specific bathymetric properties and varying environmental conditions between open sea and coastal sampling stations (Laine et al., 2007; Jakobsson et al., 2019). However, NBP sub-basin does not include coastal sites in the study area and the open sea soft-bottom monitoring stations have suffered from severe hypoxia since 1990s (Laine et al., 2007; Conley et al., 2009), and therefore this area is not included in this study regarding soft-bottom macrozoobenthos. Åland Sea and Archipelago Sea are considered as one of the HELCOM level 2 sub-basins, even though Archipelago Sea is a relatively shallow sea area, whereas Åland Sea includes the deepest parts of the study area on the Western side of the Åland islands (Jakobsson et al., 2019). Therefore, all open sea samples from this sub-basin have been taken from the deep Åland Sea stations, whereas coastal samples have been taken from shallower areas of the Åland Sea and Archipelago Sea. The rest of the sub-basins (GoF, BS, BB and Q) contain both open sea and coastal monitoring stations and they were assessed in the D2C2 and D2C3 assessments separately.

National biological monitoring and sampling approaches rely on HELCOM Cooperative Monitoring in the Baltic Marine Environment (COMBINE) program, which includes detailed monitoring guidance for phytoplankton, mesozooplankton, soft-bottom macrozoobenthos, phyto-benthic plant and animal communities, as well as coastal fishes (HELCOM, 2017). In short, monitoring of coastal fishes is conducted once per year between July and August with gill nets that are 45 m wide and extend down to 10 m depths for each site (Syke, 2020). The gill nets are in place for one day and all individuals are identified, counted and weighed using the catch per unit effort (CPUE) method (Lehikoinen et al., 2017).

Soft-bottom macrozoobenthos are sampled using benthic grabs of different size (the grab size is recorded for each sample), and all

specimens are identified, and counted from sieves of 1- and 0,5 mm mesh size (Syke, 2020). Coastal soft-bottom macrozoobenthos samples are taken throughout the summer, whereas the open sea samples are taken early June, once per year (Syke, 2020). Sampling of the spatial extent and species associated with hard-bottom macrophyte, and mussel communities is conducted with diving surveys that include the collection of bladder wracks, as well as identification and counts of the species associated within the bladder wrack communities (Rinne et al., 2021). However, the sampling of species associated within the bladder wrack communities was not added to this regime until 2020 (Syke, 2020).

Zooplankton samples are taken vertically from the entire water column with a 100 µm WP-2 plankton net (open sea zooplankton) and a handheld 100 µm plankton net (coastal zooplankton) and analysed for species composition and abundance. Phytoplankton samples are taken with a Limnos water sampler (coastal phytoplankton) or Hydrobios/Rosette water samplers (open sea phytoplankton) as several subsamples from the surface to 10 m depth, depending on the water transparency (Syke, 2020). Phytoplankton species larger than 2 µm are identified from the samples, and the composition, and abundance of these communities are analysed (HELCOM, 2017; Syke, 2020).

In addition, Contracting Parties of HELCOM and the Oslo-Paris Convention (OSPAR) have jointly developed a port monitoring protocol that has been used for the monitoring of aquatic NIS in major ports of the Baltic Sea and North-East Atlantic Ocean since 2012 (HELCOM and OSPAR, 2020). Furthermore, since 2021 HELCOM monitoring Guidelines contain description on several monitoring approaches that address newly introduced NIS, but these monitoring approaches are relatively new and not yet routinely used in most countries (HELCOM, 2021). Therefore, the NIS records obtained from port surveys and new monitoring assessments are applicable for assessing new species arrivals, but not changes within the various native species communities, since there are no long-term datasets available using these monitoring strategies.

Additionally, NIS records from research projects and verified citizen science observations (Lehtiniemi et al., 2020) have been included in the distribution analyses for secondary criterion D2C2. Secondary criterion D2C3 analyses were conducted using national monitoring data only, as these data have been collected and analysed using standardised methods that are required for the representative and reliable assessment of the proportions of species groups, adversely altered by NIS. All NIS records have been verified via morphological methods or genetic analyses, and they have been recorded to the Finnish national monitoring databases (https://www.syke.fi/en-US/Open_information/Open_web_service/Environmental_data_API) and online citizen science portals (<https://vieraslajit.fi/> and <https://kalahavainnot.luke.fi/>).

Table 2

Monitoring frequency and the number of Finnish marine monitoring stations for soft-bottom macrozoobenthos, fishes, zooplankton, phytoplankton, and macrophytes divided according to HELCOM level 2 sub-basin delineation (Syke, 2020). *There are biological research stations in the Archipelago Sea, where several biological samples are taken 10 times a year. Otherwise, the temporal resolution of monitoring in the monitoring stations within these sub-basins is same as elsewhere, 1–2 times per year.

Taxonomic group (Monitoring frequency)	Soft-bottom macrozoo-benthos (Once per year)	Fish (Once per year)	Zooplankton (1–2 times per year in the open sea, 1–12 times per year in coastal stations)	Phytoplankton (1–2 times per year in the open sea, 1–12 times per year in coastal stations)	Hard-bottom macrophyte & mussel communities (Once per year)
Sub-basin	Number of open sea/coastal monitoring stations (First monitoring year for open sea/coastal stations)				
Åland Sea and Archipelago Sea	4/165	4/7	1/5	1/43	0/70
Bothnian Bay	1964/1990	2002	1979/1960*	1979/1985	1993
Bothnian Sea	5/103	0/30	2/3	2/29	0/0
	1964/1985	2010	1979/2014	1979/1985	–
	11/150	0/20	2/1	2/25	0/7
Gulf of Finland	1964/1973	2010	1979/2014	1979/1985	1993
	10/265	1/25	4/10	4/21	0/23
	1964/1964	2005	1979/2014	1979/1985	1993
Northern Baltic Proper	4/0	0/0	2/0	2/0	0/0
The Quark	1964/-	–	1979/-	1979/-	–
	4/58	0/3	1/3	1/6	0/3
	1964/1990	2014	1979/2014	1979/1985	1993

2.3. Indicator assessment analyses

2.3.1. D2C1 – The number of newly introduced NIS

The current study listed all aquatic NIS and cryptogenic species (CS) that have been recorded in the Finnish marine waters by 31 December 2022. The species included in the D2C1 analysis have been listed according to the most recent advisory document for EU MSFD D2 reporting (Tsiamis et al., 2021), with a few exceptions. CS have been included in our analyses regarding primary criterion D2C1, as they were not considered native to the Finnish marine waters, even if there were uncertainties related to their origin or introduction pathway. The listed species were divided into NIS and CS, according to AquaNIS Editorial Board (2015) determination. Parasites were not reported as recommended by Tsiamis et al. (2021). Introduction pathway assessment was not conducted in the present study.

The NIS and CS listed were categorised into macrozoobenthos, fishes, zooplankton, phytoplankton, and macrophytes. NIS records from freshwaters were not included. Certain salmonids and sturgeons that were cultivated in Finnish marine waters several decades ago (AquaNIS Editorial Board, 2015; Ruban, 2020) have not been listed due to their inability to form self-sustaining populations and discontinuity of the records (Ojaveer et al., 2017; Tsiamis et al., 2021). The only taxa not assessed to the species level in D2C1 analysis was *Murchisonella* sp. These gastropods were first detected in Finnish marine waters in 2013, but have not been identified to species level, as the phylogeny of various heterobranch groups remains severely understudied (Dinapoli and Klussmann-Kolb, 2010). Further, the taxonomy and genetic variability of the genus *Marenzelleria* has been thoroughly revised since the genus was first recorded in the Baltic Sea and three, morphologically extremely similar species (*M. arctica*, *M. neglecta* and *M. viridis*) have been identified from the benthic communities of the study area. All of them are non-indigenous to the Baltic Sea (Hietanen et al., 2007; Kauppi et al., 2015). Therefore, they are included in the D2C1 analysis as three distinct species with the introduction year recorded as 1990, which is the first detection year of the genus. The three distinct species were identified with genetic analyses several years later, and it is unknown which year each of these species were truly present for the first time in Finnish marine waters. In addition, *Marenzelleria* spp. have not been identified to species level in the Finnish monitoring samples due to their high abundance and morphological similarity, and therefore, they were all labelled as *Marenzelleria* spp. in the D2C2 and D2C3 analyses.

It has been recommended that the primary criterion D2C1 should be assessed regionally for six-year assessment periods, and the number of comparable, previous six-year assessment cycles should be based on the regional history of monitoring intensity (Tsiamis et al., 2021). The first six-year assessment period assessed regionally for the Baltic Sea was made for 2011–2016 (HELCOM, 2018), and the second assessment (2016–2021) overlapped by a year with the previous assessment (HELCOM, 2023a). In the current study, the first HELCOM assessment period (2011–2016) was utilised as a reference point, and the next and previous six-year assessment periods (namely 1987–1992, 1993–1998, 1999–2004, 2005–2010, and 2017–2022) were calculated from this period for this national assessment without the overlap. Previous six-year assessment periods used in the present study were assessed back to the period of 1987–1992 regarding the D2C1 analysis, as most monitoring efforts listed in Table 2 were in place by 1987. It shall be noted that the assessment period of 2017–2022 may not include all most recent NIS, if new species are identified from the 2022 samples in the future, since all samples had not been analysed yet due to limited microscopist resources.

2.3.2. D2C2 – Abundance and spatial distribution of established NIS

As the national marine monitoring program does not specifically target NIS and the monitoring effort is not temporally sufficient for all taxonomic groups (monitoring coastal fishes with gill nets is not reliable, nor quantitative for demersal fish species, Adjers et al., 2006), it would

have not been representative to perform abundance analyses for all established NIS and CS. Therefore, the spatial distribution analyses were conducted as case studies for established, non-indigenous taxa, namely *Cercopagis pengoi* (zooplankton), *Marenzelleria* spp. (soft-bottom macrozoobenthos) and *Neogobius melanostomus* (fish) from 1993 to 2022. This was done by mapping the presence of these taxa for each assessment period. New records represented their spread across the six sub-basins within the Finnish marine waters over time. Additionally, absence of *Marenzelleria* spp. was mapped to indicate benthic monitoring stations that were sampled without detecting the taxa. The absence data were not included for *C. pengoi* and *N. melanostomus*, since limited number of monitoring stations for zooplankton and coastal fishes did not allow to assess their absence reliably. Another assessment of distribution – frequency of *Marenzelleria* spp. occurrence – was assessed by calculating the percentage of the presence of the taxa in all coastal and open sea samples for each sub-basin over time. This was not possible for *C. pengoi* and *N. melanostomus* as the monitoring for zooplankton is not frequent enough to assess population changes, and there is no routine monitoring in place for demersal fishes. The abundance assessment was only done for *Marenzelleria* spp., since high monitoring effort for open sea and coastal soft-bottom macrozoobenthos enabled such assessment. The abundance analysis included comparing changes in abundance of *Marenzelleria* spp. (calculated in the mean number of individuals per unit area [m^2]).

2.3.3. D2C3 – Proportion of a species group adversely altered due to NIS

The secondary criterion D2C3 assessment was conducted for coastal and open sea soft-bottom macrozoobenthos. In this assessment, all soft-bottom macrozoobenthos data from 1993 to 2022 that have been recorded to the Finnish national monitoring database by 1 May 2023 were obtained. The coastal macrozoobenthos datapoints were obtained as the mean abundance of each taxon per sampling visit (three to five benthic grab samples per visit), whereas the open sea datapoints were not averaged in the national monitoring database (datapoints included taxa abundances for each grab sample). As monitoring of the soft-bottom benthic communities was not begun simultaneously in all study areas and the number of monitoring stations also differ between the sub-basins, there were differences in the number of datapoints obtained (Table 3).

Most species were recorded at species level in the complete 1993–2022 dataset. However, as all taxa were not identified to species level regarding all sub-basins, higher taxonomic level (e.g., genus level) was used for the following taxa; *Marenzelleria*, *Murchisonella*, *Hydrachnidia*, *Jaera*, as well as all insects (*Ephemerellidae*, *Heptageniidae*, *Caenidae*, *Baetidae*, *Platycnemididae*, *Coenagrionidae*, *Aeshnidae*, *Corduliidae*, *Sialidae*, *Libellulidae*, *Corixidae*, *Rhyacophilidae*, *Hydroptilidae*, *Polycentropodidae*, *Hydropsychidae*, *Phryganeidae*, *Lepidostomatidae*, *Molanidae*, *Limnephilidae*, *Leptoceridae*, *Psychomyiidae*, *Ecnomidae*, *Pyralidae*, *Crambidae*, *Psychodidae*, *Chaoboridae*, *Culicidae*, *Chironomidae*, *Elmidae*, *Ceratopogonidae*, *Tipulidae*, *Limoniidae*, *Tabanidae*, *Ephydriidae*, *Halipilidae*, *Dytiscidae*, *Hydrophilidae*, *Chrysomelidae*).

Perhaps the most notable methodological aspect in these D2C3 analyses was the exclusion of datapoints, where there were no benthic animals at all. This exclusion was made, since samples are not taken from anoxic stations during the monitoring cruises. The exclusion of these, no life-samples inevitably affected the D2C3 analyses for the Gulf of Finland, since this sea area has suffered considerably from large-scale hypoxia (Laine et al., 2007; Berezina et al., 2017). Due to expanding areas of hypoxia/anoxia, fewer number of samples are taken from the Gulf of Finland, and the representation of the results in the present study concerns only those samples, where taxa were detected. However, anoxic conditions do not occur in other sub-basins of the study area.

As mentioned in the introduction, there is no unified methodology to address secondary criterion D2C3 (Tsiamis et al., 2021). To address this gap, the D2C3 assessment in the present study represented changes in NIS proportion (NIS individuals divided by all individuals in a specific

Table 3

Number of datapoints for open sea and coastal soft-bottom macrozoobenthos for each sub-basin and assessment period in the D2C3 analyses of the present study. The main causes to different sample sizes were the uneven number of sampling stations per sub-basin, as well as different starting years of monitoring. Further, samples are not taken at all from anoxic sampling stations, and their number has fluctuated throughout the assessment periods in the Gulf of Finland (Berezina et al., 2017). *Limited resources regarding microscopist expertise have resulted in smaller number of datapoints that have been assessed for the 2017 – 2022 assessment period.

Open sea datapoints						
Sub-basin	1993–1998	1999–2004	2005–2010	2011–2016	2017–2022*	Total
Åland Sea	32	33	32	33	23	153
Bothnian Bay	157	133	124	95	66	575
Bothnian Sea	113	142	171	122	125	673
Gulf of Finland	242	116	100	181	38	677
The Quark	38	39	45	27	36	185
Total	582	463	472	458	288	2263
Coastal datapoints						
Archipelago Sea	0	47	576	1370	381	2374
Bothnian Bay	0	0	261	765	517	1543
Bothnian Sea	0	0	217	503	376	1096
Gulf of Finland	136	254	739	3056	355	4540
The Quark	0	0	193	604	320	1117
Total	136	301	1986	6298	1949	10,670

Table 4

NIS and CS introductions in Finnish marine waters until 31 December 2022.

Species	NIS/CS	Year of first observation	Taxonomic group
<i>Mya arenaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	CS	1200	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Amphibalanus improvisus</i> (Darwin, 1854)	CS	1800 s	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Cordylophora caspia</i> (Pallas, 1771)	CS/NIS	1800	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Elodea canadensis</i> Michx.	NIS	1870 s	Macrophyte
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	NIS	1898	Fish
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (J.E. Gray, 1843)	NIS	1920	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Acartia</i> (<i>Acanthacartia</i>) <i>tonsa</i> (Dana, 1849)	NIS	1930	Zooplankton
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1853)	NIS	1933	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	NIS	1958	Fish
<i>Boccardiella ligerica</i> (Ferroinière, 1898)	NIS	1963	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Marenzelleria arctica</i> (Chamberlin, 1920)	NIS	Since 1990	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Marenzelleria neglecta</i> (Sikorski & Bick, 2004)	NIS		Macrozoobenthos
<i>Marenzelleria viridis</i> (Verrill, 1873)	NIS		Macrozoobenthos
<i>Cercopagis</i> (<i>Cercopagis</i>) <i>pengoi</i> (Ostroumov, 1891)	NIS	1992	Zooplankton
<i>Hemimysis anomala</i> (G.O. Sars, 1907)	NIS	1992	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Proocentrum cordatum</i> (Ostenfeldt) J.D.Dodge, 1976	CS	1993	Phytoplankton
<i>Dreissena polymorpha</i> (Pallas, 1771)	NIS	1995	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Evadne anonyx</i> (G.O. Sars, 1897)	NIS	1998	Zooplankton
<i>Gammarus tigrinus</i> (Sexton, 1939)	NIS	2003	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Mytilopsis leucophaeata</i> (Conrad, 1831)	NIS	2003	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Palaemon elegans</i> (Rathke, 1836)	CS	2003	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Chara connivens</i> (P.Salzmann ex A.Braun, 1835)	NIS	2004	Macrophyte
<i>Carassius gibelio</i> (Bloch, 1782)	NIS	2005	Fish
<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i> (Pallas, 1814)	NIS	2005	Fish
<i>Paranais frici</i> (Hrabě, 1941)	NIS	2008	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Telmatogeton japonicus</i> (Tokunaga, 1933)	NIS	2008	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i> (Gould, 1841)	NIS	2009	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Maeotias marginata</i> (Modeer, 1791)	NIS	2012	Zooplankton
<i>Murchisonella</i> (Mörch, 1875) (<i>genus</i>)	NIS	2013	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Laonome xeprovala</i> (Bick & Bastrop, in Bick et al., 2018)	NIS	2014	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Sinelobus vanhaareni</i> (Bamber, 2014)	NIS	2016	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Nippoleucon hinumensis</i> (Gamo, 1967)	NIS	2021	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Rangia cuneata</i> (G. B. Sowerby I, 1832)	NIS	2021	Macrozoobenthos
<i>Proterorhinus semipellucidus</i> (Kessler, 1877)	NIS	2022	Fish

species group recorded for each datapoint) over time and aimed at considering how these changes have impacted the biodiversity of the local soft-bottom macrozoobenthos communities in coastal and open sea areas. There has been a lot of debate on the use of different species diversity metrics regarding sampling effort, as well as the species communities and regions of interest (Jost, 2006; Chase and Knight, 2013; Roswell et al., 2021). A diversity metric often described as the Gini-Simpson index refers to the probability that two individuals drawn from the same sample will be of different species (0 to 1, the closer the index is to 1, the more diverse the community) (Jost, 2006; Chase and Knight, 2013). This index is insensitive to changes in sampling effort

(Chase and Knight, 2013), which was important since sampling effort varied spatially and temporally between sub-basins and assessment periods. Anyway, Gini-Simpson index refers only to the probability that two randomly drawn individuals from a sample are of different species, and extremely similar probabilities can be obtained with variable number of species within a sample. Therefore, the Gini-Simpson index was calculated for each datapoint and multiplied by species richness in the present study. As these measures are indicators of species richness and diversity, but not representative of the total biodiversity of a community (Ieno et al., 2006; Norling et al., 2007), phyla richness (Porifera, Cnidaria, Platyhelminthes, Nemertea, Priapulida, Annelida, Mollusca,

Bryozoa and Arthropoda) was also determined for each datapoint. Finally, phyla richness was multiplied with the Gini-Simpson index and species richness for each datapoint to provide an indication of the total biodiversity. Using such combination of measures holds the assumption that the more species and phyla and the higher the probability that two individuals drawn from a sample are of different taxa, the higher is the total biodiversity of the community. This measure was labelled as community biodiversity index (CBI) to indicate the diversity within the soft-bottom macrozoobenthos communities of the study area, as follows;

$$CBI = \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^S p_i^2\right) \times \text{Species richness} \times \text{Phyla richness}$$

Eventually, NIS proportion and CBI were calculated for each datapoint, and trends in these metrics were observed over time (from 1993 to 2022). Furthermore, correlation analysis between NIS proportion and the CBI was conducted to detect if the recorded NIS proportion correlated with CBI within the soft-bottom benthic macrozoobenthos communities. A non-parametric Spearman correlation analysis was used since the data were not normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov, $p < 0.001$). This was done for all open sea and coastal datapoints. Visual observation of the correlation graphs between NIS proportion and CBI indicated that the correlations appeared non-monotonic. The correlation was positive when NIS proportion was relatively low but turned negative with an increasing NIS proportion. This suggested the categorisation into lower and higher NIS proportion samples, which was done based on the median NIS proportion for all samples (median NIS proportion was 0,174). Finally, additional Spearman correlation analyses were conducted for open sea and coastal data points with low ($<0,174$) and high NIS proportions ($\geq 0,174$) to detect how NIS proportion above and below the median correlated with the CBI. The statistical analyses for the D2C3 assessment were conducted using SPSS version 27, IBM, Chicago, IL, USA.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. D2C1 – The number of newly introduced NIS to Finnish sea areas

34 NIS and CS have been recorded in the Finnish marine waters until 31 December 2022. Majority of these taxa (64,7 %) have been macrozoobenthos, followed by fishes (14,7 %), zooplankton (11,8 %), macrophytes (5,9 %), and phytoplankton (2,9 %) (Table 4, Fig. 1). 24 of the introductions have been recorded since 1990, and the annual rate of new introductions has fluctuated between 0,5 and 0,83 new introductions per year over the last six assessment periods (Fig. 2).

The national assessment on trends in new NIS arrivals to the Finnish marine waters (D2C1) indicated that the number of marine NIS in Finnish waters has more than doubled since the assessment period of 1987–1992, and these new taxa have arrived quite steadily over the last 30 years. Further, this outcome suggests that Finnish marine waters did not reach GES for the primary criterion D2C1 (HELCOM, 2018, 2023a) in 2017–2022, as three new NIS (*Nippoleucon hinumensis*, *Proterorhinus semipellucidus* and *Rangia cuneata*) were detected during this period and two of them (*N. hinumensis* and *P. semipellucidus*) were not previously recorded in the Baltic Sea.

The increase in new NIS arrivals into Finnish marine waters is concerning and several potential causes can be suggested. First, the intensification of globalisation through maritime trade and its' impact cannot be ignored. International trade has multiplied 2.5-fold in millions of tonnes of total cargo loaded on ships from 1990 to 2020 (UNCTAD, 2021). Secondly, implementation of the Ballast Water Management Convention is still in progress (Outinen et al., 2021; IMO, 2023a), while the recently reviewed Biofouling Guidelines for internationally trading ships are not legally binding (IMO, 2023b) and lag even further behind.

Pathway analysis was not conducted in the present study, but potential pathways for the introduced species can be speculated regardless. Introduction pathways of marine NIS are generally divided into six main categories; i) corridors, ii) escapees from confinement, iii) releases in nature, iv) transport contaminants, v) transport stowaway and, vi) unaided introductions (Bailey et al., 2020). Further, it is essential to note that a NIS may have various modes of spread, as for example in the global spread of zebra mussels (Pollux et al., 2010). Corridor pathway includes spread through anthropogenically constructed interconnecting waterways and enlarged canals, which are relevant to the study area, since several NIS recorded from Finnish marine areas originate from the Ponto-Caspian region through man-made waterways (Ojaveer et al., 2017). However, it remains unknown whether these species have been able to spread through the waterways without the aid of shipping vectors. Escapees from confinement, transport contaminants and unaided introductions are the least likely pathways to most NIS recorded from the Finnish sea areas, as none of them are known of being typical aquarium species, known contaminants or parasites on plants and animals, or known to be unaided introductions associated with floating anthropogenic materials. Further, releases in nature and escapees from confinement are likely to be responsible for the introduction of only two species, *Carassius gibelio* and *Hemimysis anomala*, which have been deliberately released into the adjacent waters in the past (Ojaveer et al., 2017). However, transport stowaway, including shipping vectors (ballast water, fouling and hitchhikers on ships) can be considered as the most likely introduction pathway for the majority of the 24 NIS recorded

Fig. 1. Cumulative increase of new marine NIS and CS in Finland.

Fig. 2. Annual rate of new NIS introductions for each assessment period since 1987.

from Finnish sea areas since 1987, although there is often little to no evidence of this (Ojaveer et al., 2017; Bailey et al., 2020).

Increased research and monitoring efforts may have further improved the detection frequency of new taxa (Zenetos et al., 2022), as global and regional policies have continuously encouraged nations to improve their care for the environment since the end of the 20th century. This started nearly 30 years ago, when the United Nations' Convention on Biological Diversity entered into force, aiming towards the conservation of biological diversity and sustainable use of its components (UNEP, 1994). EU MSFD followed this agreement shortly in the early 21st century, highlighting the importance of environmental and marine monitoring (Lehtiniemi et al., 2015; EC, 2017). MSFD is further interlinked with the new EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, aiming to strengthen the protection of marine ecosystems and highlighting the need for ecosystem-based approaches to the management of anthropogenic activities at sea (Tsiamis et al., 2021). These policy and legislative advancements over the past few decades may have led to more intensive monitoring efforts, as well as potentially earlier detections of new NIS introductions. However, it shall be noted that the monitoring of physical, chemical and biological parameters within the open sea and coastal areas of the Baltic Sea have been regionally coordinated through HELCOM already since the late 1970s (HELCOM, 2017), and there are relatively detailed species records published already much earlier than the beginning of the 21st century (e.g., on *Boccardiella ligerica* by Eliason and Haahntela (1969), and *Cercopagis pengoi* by Ojaveer and Lumberg (1995)). In addition, the Finnish biological marine monitoring program (Syke, 2020) included already majority of its components in the 1990s, and most of the first sightings of new NIS are made by research projects or citizens (Lehtiniemi et al., 2020). Therefore, increased routine monitoring efforts over the late 20th and early 21st centuries are not likely the main causes of increased NIS records in Finland, even though these efforts are crucial to assess potential impacts of established NIS on native species communities.

3.2. D2C2 – Abundance and spatial distribution of established NIS

Marenzelleria spp. was first detected from the Finnish marine waters in 1990, followed by the first record of *C. pengoi* in 1992. Both taxa were first detected in the Gulf of Finland from national monitoring samples. Distribution of *Marenzelleria* spp. covered all sub-basins already during the assessment period of 1999–2004 and the spread expanded remarkably in coastal and open sea areas within all sub-basins in the following years (Figs. 3 and 4, Table 5). The distribution of *C. pengoi* covered all sub-basins within the study area by 1999–2004, except the Quark, where the species was first detected from monitoring samples during the

period of 2011–2016. It is difficult to estimate the true distribution and abundance of *C. pengoi*, due to insufficient spatial and temporal resolution of the monitoring effort of pelagic zooplankton within the study area. Round goby (*N. melanostomus*) was first detected by a fisherman from Archipelago Sea, Southwestern Finland, in 2005, and its' distribution covered all sub-basins but the Quark already during the following assessment period (2011–2016). New records of the round goby have emerged 2017 onwards, but there are still no records from the Quark.

It appears that the Finnish biological monitoring program (Syke, 2020) is relatively sufficient to address the spatial distribution of a few established NIS nationally, at least on the HELCOM level 2 (sub-basin delineation, HELCOM, 2022) spatial level. To conduct such assessment, one simply needs to determine establishment status of NIS, as well as have presence data of these taxa to assess whether the established NIS of interest have spread into new sub-basins. However, if one wishes to conduct such assessment for all 22 benthic broad habitat types as described in EC (2017), or use higher spatial resolution (e.g., distribution within a sub-basin), the spatial coverage of national monitoring is inevitably insufficient. For example, monitoring of sessile and mobile epifauna on hard seabed substrata (Outinen et al., 2019) was added to the national marine monitoring programme in 2021 and there are no long-term data available for these communities.

To address changes in abundance of established NIS, the temporal resolution of Finnish marine biological monitoring program is even more insufficient, which hampers conducting representative D2C2 assessments. Due to fast reproduction cycles and vulnerability to prevailing seasonal conditions concerning phyto- and zooplankton communities (Klais et al., 2016; Kuhn et al., 2019), more frequent sampling regime than 1–2 samples per year is needed to assess changes in abundance within the associated communities (Klais et al., 2016).

D2C2 abundance assessments on demersal fishes equally suffer from similar drawbacks, as using gill nets instead of trawling methods, is not an efficient approach to sample demersal fish species quantitatively (Ådjers et al., 2006). Therefore, the abundance of non-indigenous gobies, or the community composition of demersal fishes cannot be assessed with the current monitoring strategies. These insufficiencies are concerning, since non-indigenous gobies compete with native demersal fishes for nutrition in the Baltic Sea (Karlson et al., 2007). Finally, diving surveys associated with the monitoring of hard-bottom macrophyte, and mussel communities started already in the 1990s, but the invertebrate sampling from bladderwrack communities was added to this regime only in 2020 (Syke, 2020), hence the monitoring of these communities is still at early stages. Altogether, these spatial, temporal, and methodological limitations were the main reason why the distribution of established NIS were only analysed for three non-indigenous taxa.

Fig. 3. Changes in the distribution of the NIS records for *C. pengoi* (green dots), *Marenzelleria* spp. (yellow dots) and *N. melanostomus* (red dots) from the assessment period of 1993–1998 to 2011–2016. Black dots refer to *Marenzelleria* spp. absence. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. The most recent distribution (2017–2022) of the NIS records for *C. pengoi* (green dots), *Marenzelleria* spp. (yellow dots) and *N. melanostomus* (red dots). Black dots refer to *Marenzelleria* spp. absence. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Several soft-bottom benthic monitoring stations have been sampled for more than 50 years already in the Finnish marine waters, which allows a very good long-term temporal resolution for assessing these communities, even though the spatial coverage of monitoring could be improved (Nygård et al., 2020). Therefore, these data enabled assessing the changes in occurrence and abundance of the *Marenzelleria* spp. over time. Furthermore, *Marenzelleria* spp. was chosen for this abundance case study, since the invasion of the genus has been one of the most extensive in the northern Baltic Sea (Kauppi et al., 2015).

The abundance of *Marenzelleria* spp. reached peak levels in the open sea monitoring stations in 2005–2010 in all sub-basins, except the Bothnian Bay (Table 5). In all open sea sampling stations except the

Bothnian Bay, *Marenzelleria* spp. abundances started to decrease, following a so-called boom-and-bust pattern (Rudnick et al., 2003; Simberloff and Gibbons, 2004; Kauppi et al., 2015). Interesting differences in the trends between coastal and open sea samples were detected, as the abundance of *Marenzelleria* spp. decreased since 2005–2010, but again increased after 2011–2016 in coastal sampling stations. In addition, the percentage of *Marenzelleria* spp. presence in soft-bottom macrozoobenthos samples appeared to be growing until the most recent assessment period.

Even though the invasion of *Marenzelleria* spp. followed the boom-and-bust pattern in most sub-basins at the open sea benthic communities, contradicting and irregular invasion patterns were detected in the coastal areas, suggesting that invasions even among the same taxa are challenging to predict within the recipient environment and habitats. Further, Simberloff and Gibbons (2004) have reviewed situations where a ‘boom’ or ‘bust’ of an introduced species may never occur, which can be particularly true for isolated or geographically remote environments. Biologically, Finnish sea areas, and particularly open sea benthic communities represent relatively species poor communities with only a handful of commonly present taxa, where *Marenzelleria* spp. have very few competitors (Kauppi et al., 2015). The observed changes and differences in *Marenzelleria* spp. abundance among coastal benthic communities between the sub-basins support the conclusion that the invasion pattern of an introduced species/taxon depends heavily on several environmental conditions within the invaded regions. The *Marenzelleria* spp. abundance case study suggests that a reliable and representative completion of the assessment requires region-specific, or even site-specific evaluation. For example, zebra mussel *Dreissena polymorpha* is one of the most well-known freshwater invaders globally. It took *D. polymorpha* nearly 200 years to reach the Gulf of Finland, after prior introduction in the Curonian lagoon in the Southern Baltic Sea (Pollux et al., 2010), indicating that the species has not gradually invaded new regions in the Baltic Sea. *Marenzelleria* species complex is perhaps the most studied non-indigenous taxon in the Baltic Sea, and even after several impact studies on native biota (as presented in Kauppi et al., 2015), it is evident that NIS impacts on local species communities cannot be generalised over various biogeographic regions or sub-basins.

3.3. D2C3 – Proportion of a species group adversely altered due to NIS

NIS proportion and CBI varied between the studied assessment periods and sub-basins for both, open sea and coastal macrozoobenthos communities (Figs. 5 and 6), and clear temporal trends were not observed. Regarding open sea benthic communities, NIS proportion was highest in the Gulf of Finland, Åland Sea and the Quark, reaching > 60

Table 5

Changes in *Marenzelleria* spp. abundances and the percentages of macrozoobenthos datapoints, where *Marenzelleria* spp. were present over the last six assessment periods in coastal and open sea areas. Monitoring data were not available (NA) for most of the coastal sub-basins regarding the 1987–1992, 1993–1998 and 1999–2004 assessment periods.

Assessment period	Mean density (per m ²)/Presence percentage in all datapoints				
	Open sea datapoints				
	GoF	AS/NBP	BB	BS	Q
1987–1992	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %
1993–1998	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %	0 / 0 %	0,08 / 1 %	0,23 / 3 %
1999–2004	0,13 / 2 %	498 / 32 %	0,2 / 1 %	11 / 20 %	411 / 52 %
2005–2010	343 / 77 %	785 / 94 %	0,43 / 4 %	761 / 90 %	756 / 76 %
2011–2016	261 / 91 %	324 / 86 %	35 / 34 %	453 / 98 %	421 / 100 %
2017–2022	248 / 95 %	338 / 94 %	48 / 69 %	241 / 98 %	373 / 100 %
	Coastal datapoints				
1987–1992	3 / 25 %	NA	NA	NA	NA
1993–1998	69 / 58 %	NA	NA	NA	NA
1999–2004	54 / 53 %	31 / 47 %	NA	NA	NA
2005–2010	630 / 80 %	810 / 83 %	13 / 37 %	224 / 85 %	322 / 63 %
2011–2016	404 / 64 %	424 / 67 %	94 / 35 %	129 / 56 %	259 / 57 %
2017–2022	639 / 78 %	611 / 76 %	341 / 76 %	367 / 82 %	368 / 68 %

Fig. 5. NIS proportion and CBI in the open sea soft-bottom macrozoobenthos communities for each sub-basin and assessment period. The columns represent the mean NIS proportion and CBI, while the error bars are presenting the standard error.

Fig. 6. NIS proportion and CBI in the coastal soft-bottom macrozoobenthos communities for each sub-basin and assessment period. The columns represent the mean NIS proportion and CBI, while the error bars are presenting the standard error.

Fig. 7. The correlation between NIS proportion and CBI in coastal and open sea soft-bottom benthic communities with low (<0,174) and high (≥0,174) NIS proportion. Linear trendlines were added for illustration of the increasing or decreasing trends.

%, whereas it was lowest in the Bothnian Bay. CBI showed somewhat of an increasing trend in the open sea benthic communities of all studied sub-basins, except Åland Sea, where CBI has clearly decreased since the assessment period of 2005–2010. NIS proportion and CBI showed similar results for coastal benthic communities of the study area. Overall, CBI was highest in the southernmost sub-basins (Gulf of Finland and Åland/Archipelago Sea), and lowest in Bothnian Bay. These findings were somewhat expected, as previous research by Bonsdorff (2006) and Laine et al. (2007) have noted that coastal habitats and the southernmost sea regions of the study area have higher biodiversity in comparison to the open sea areas, as well as northern, less saline Baltic Sea sub-basins, particularly in areas where hypoxia does not affect the communities.

NIS proportion correlated significantly with the CBI in the open sea and coastal benthic communities (Appendices B and C). However, visual observations of the sub-basin level correlations (Appendix C) indicated that lower NIS proportions resulted in increasing CBI for almost all sub-basins, whereas higher NIS proportions remarkably decreased the CBI. Therefore, the median NIS proportion was calculated for all data points and the correlation between low NIS proportion and the CBI, as well as a high NIS proportion and the CBI showed even clearer trends (Fig. 7). In short, when NIS occupied less than 17,4 % of the benthic communities, NIS proportion correlated positively with the CBI ($\rho = 0.365$, $p < 0.001$ and $\rho = 0.422$, $p < 0.001$, for open sea and coastal benthic communities, respectively), suggesting that lower proportions of NIS increased the local CBI in all benthic communities. Nevertheless, the outcome was the opposite regarding data points where NIS proportion was 17,4 % or higher, as significantly negative correlations were detected for the open sea ($\rho = -0.722$, $p < 0.001$), and coastal ($\rho = -0.615$, $p < 0.001$) communities.

Even though NIS proportion correlated significantly with the CBI in relation to the studied benthic communities, there may have been other

confounding environmental factors that have simultaneously affected the biological diversity of these communities. Stratification-induced hypoxia and salinity are very likely the most critical environmental factors affecting the composition and biodiversity of benthic communities within the Gulf of Finland (Laine et al., 2007; Kauppi et al., 2015). Stratification-induced hypoxia may have various impacts to the current results, since samples are not taken at all from stations that have no oxygen near the seabed (Syke, 2020). Therefore, less and less samples are being taken from the hypoxic Gulf of Finland, and the only samples taken are from areas that do not suffer from anoxia. It may appear that the biodiversity has increased in the open sea benthic communities of the Gulf of Finland, even though the number of samples taken has decreased severely, and the most recently obtained datapoints are from the sampling stations that are rich in oxygen.

The present findings are limited to the benthic communities of the study area, and similar assessments are needed from other regions to assess the impacts of already established NIS. Nevertheless, as shown by the temporal trends and correlations presented in this study, the increase in NIS arrivals to the Finnish marine waters since 1987 has clearly elevated the proportions of NIS in local open sea and coastal benthic communities, and this increase correlates significantly with the changes in local biodiversity. The highly significant negative correlation between NIS proportion above the median and CBI suggests that when NIS begin to dominate these communities, biodiversity of the community decreases, and the local benthic communities are less likely to have a diverse and heterogenous structure. Similar observations have been also made previously on NIS that reach locally high densities and become dominant, such as *D. polymorpha* in the Great Lakes, and *Potamocorbula amurensis* in San Francisco Bay (Ruiz et al., 1997).

Fig. 8. CBI compared to species richness and Hill-Simpson diversity index that give more weight to rare and common species, respectively (described and calculated according to Roswell et al., 2021).

3.4. Methodological considerations

Several NIS inventories, updates, and indicator assessments, such as Ojaveer et al. (2017), Tsiamis et al. (2019), Staehr et al. (2020), Ojaveer et al. (2021), Zenetos et al. (2022), Massé et al. (2023) and Png-Gonzalez et al. (2023) have been published recently. While each of these publications has demonstrated a valuable contribution to the advancement of the field and addressed several important issues, common consensus on the evaluation of impacts of already established NIS seems to be missing.

The CBI introduced here is a measure for biodiversity, and it should be used to detect changes in biodiversity within or between the marine areas of interest. Various species diversity measures have been created in the past, and the use of these indices under various conditions have been extensively discussed, mainly because they measure species diversity differently (Jost, 2006; Chase and Knight, 2013; Roswell et al., 2021). CBI is not solely a species diversity index, as it expands traditional species diversity measures by combining phyla richness, Gini-Simpson index, and species richness. The difference between CBI and species diversity indices can be seen particularly in samples with higher biodiversity (Fig. 8). While the Hill-Simpson and species richness scores increased by 260 % and 240 %, respectively, between the median and 95th percentile datapoint for all coastal areas, CBI increased by nearly 528 % (Fig. 8). Adding a higher taxonomic level (phylum) count to species diversity measures combines several diversity measures into one index, and it is a more reasonable measure for total biodiversity than species diversity indices that consider all species as single and equivalent units (Bertrand et al., 2006). Furthermore, CBI offers a potential solution to the issue described in the HELCOM Holistic Assessment on biodiversity that no methods address the status of the entire food web (HELCOM, 2023b). As the CBI depends on the taxonomic diversity of the organisms present in a sample/area, it can be calculated for all species groups separately and the index scores could be combined for a biodiversity measure of the entire food web of the area.

Nevertheless, utilising a higher ranked taxon (phylum) as a factor in the CBI may not be a flawless approach, since all taxa are not monophyletic (Bertrand et al., 2006), and one alternative would be assessing several taxonomic levels separately (Briski et al., 2023). In addition,

another option would be to measure the functional biodiversity of a community by utilising functional group richness to demonstrate the range of various biological traits present in the community (Norling et al., 2007), although the main issue with the approach is that it is selective to the biological traits included, and all traits cannot be considered as equally functional (Mlambo, 2014). It is important to note that the CBI has been now only tested for soft-bottom macrozoobenthos of the northern Baltic Sea, and further testing of the index would be needed to verify its' applicability to other species communities in other marine regions. CBI will very likely provide much higher index scores for regions with naturally higher species and phyla richness, but this can be expected, as the biodiversity in such areas is equally higher.

Previously designed methodologies to measure NIS impacts, namely the BPL index (Olenin et al., 2007) and CIMPAL model (Katsanevaki et al., 2016) have a different approach, as they focus on the present NIS, but not the recipient communities. These approaches were not used in the present study since they do not directly detect NIS impacts in the recipient ecosystems. The BPL index methodology holds the assumption that the wider the distribution and the higher the abundance of NIS, the more adverse or severe is the impact (higher biopollution score together with impact). The CIMPAL approach, in turn, presumes that all NIS with studied evidence of adverse impacts in the past, will also have these adverse impacts in other regions. The results of the present study highlighted that these assumptions may not be correct even within the same sub-basin. For instance, abundance of *Marenzelleria* spp. and NIS proportion has increased over time in the open sea and coastal Bothnian Bay (Table 5, Figs. 5 and 6). Nevertheless, the impact on local macrozoobenthos has been different, as the CBI has simultaneously increased for open sea areas and decreased for coastal areas due to lower overall biodiversity in the open sea communities. Furthermore, it would be nearly impossible to assign abundance and distribution score for *Marenzelleria* spp. for the sub-basin using the BPL scoring system, as they occur in low numbers in several localities, but also in moderate or even high numbers for several other localities within the same sub-basin. Even though the BPL and CIMPAL approaches provide a lot of valuable information and may be operational in some regions, they do not reflect NIS impacts on the local species communities.

More comprehensive D2C3 assessments would require multivariate analyses of several environmental factors, such as temperature and salinity to determine the significance of the impact of various independent variables among NIS on local species communities, as D2C3 refers to 'proportion of a species group adversely altered by NIS' (EC, 2017). Such approaches have not been attempted previously according to the present knowledge, although a recent study by Staehr et al. (2020) included correlations between various environmental parameters and relative importance of NIS to the number of native species. It is a limitation of the present study that data on environmental parameters, such as temperature, salinity, and oxygen that may affect the community composition of the studied communities were not included, since these data were not available with sufficient accuracy on all sampling visits and stations. Some of these environmental conditions are highly localised (e.g., oxygen concentrations in the Gulf of Finland, Laine et al., 2007), hence pooling e.g., oxygen measurements from the entire sub-basin, or proportion of a sub-basin, would have not been a reliable option. Nonetheless, wherever data on such environmental parameters are available in combination with biological data, future studies are highly encouraged to include them in D2C3 assessments to detect the proportions of native communities, specifically altered by NIS.

3.5. Concluding remarks – The crucial importance of monitoring and management

It has been acknowledged that monitoring of aquatic NIS is insufficient in majority of the EU countries (Lehtiniemi et al., 2015; Nygård et al., 2016; Tsiamis et al., 2021). As discussed in the present study, it appears that also the temporal and spatial resolution of routine national biological monitoring programs have severe gaps concerning several species groups. More specifically, resource limitations associated with taxonomic expertise have been presented as one of the main resource gaps within the field of aquatic invasions (Costello et al., 2006; Ojaveer et al., 2017; Bailey et al., 2020). Other approaches for species identification have emerged, but even though molecular monitoring methods have evolved, several challenges, such as wider accessibility and availability of the methods and lack of reference sequences remain (Darling et al., 2017). Improvements for database development would be also very much needed, since there was considerable variation in the data entries between the older datapoints from the 1990s and the newer ones from 2010s even in the Finnish national database. These improvements would be beneficial on a larger geographical scale as well, since several distinct, international online databases exist for NIS (Costello et al., 2021), but there is no harmonisation among them. Enhanced monitoring strategies and database administration would increase the knowledge base of the policymakers and awareness of the public on the changes within the environment (Nygård et al., 2016). Routine monitoring is also a prerequisite for modelling since model calibration requires time series data.

In regional cooperation, the 2023 Holistic Assessment of the Status of the Baltic Sea reported not only gaps in the spatial and temporal coverage of the current monitoring networks, but also the inability of the individual indicator assessments to combine the relevant information into an assessment on the state of biodiversity of the whole food web (HELCOM, 2023a, 2023b). The present study provides a readily applicable methodology with CBI that enables assessing changes in biodiversity for species groups of interest over time. HELCOM has set a zero-tolerance policy on the GES threshold concerning the arrival of new NIS

(HELCOM, 2018). It can be discussed whether this is practical considering the present maritime trading volumes, but the role of scientists is to feed objective information and quantifiable solutions into decision-making processes. One of the main issues in terms of improving the environmental status is that management of new NIS introductions via maritime traffic largely follows international decision-making in International Maritime Organization, which is a lengthy and laborious process (Outinen et al., 2021). However, nothing prevents countries from protecting marine waters under their jurisdiction. For example, national ballast water management regulations have been in place in USA and Canada for years (Scriven et al., 2015; Transport Canada, 2021), and ships have been fined for breaking them (EPA, 2023). Therefore, management practices can be put in place nationally to not only prevent new introductions, but also to follow how these practices and regulations improve the environmental status. Most importantly, what is the purpose of defining GES and aiming to reach it, if there are no management actions that make them even theoretically achievable? The ultimate aim of NIS management should be preventing all introductions that can be directly managed.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Okko Outinen: Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Tarja Katajisto:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Henrik Nygård:** Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Riikka Puntila-Dodd:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Maiju Lehtiniemi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The present study was initiated by continuous updates on marine indicators within the EU that is supported by the European Topic Centre and European Environment Agency. The study would have not been possible without regional cooperation under HELCOM, or the national Finnish Marine Research Infrastructure (FINMARI) network that have provided the foundation, facilities and equipment to conduct monitoring and various projects that fed data into this submission. We would also like to thank numerous taxonomists responsible of analysing the community samples over the past decades. Further, the outcomes of the present study benefited greatly from several discussions at the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of Unesco and International Maritime Organizations' Working Group on Ballast and Other Ship Vectors, as well as the ICES Working Group on Introductions and Transfers of Marine Organisms. RP has received funding also from GES4SEAS project under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 101059877). The authors appreciate constructive feedback from two anonymous reviewers that improved the quality of the study.

Appendix A. . Map of the study area

Finnish marine waters. Sea areas within the study area according to the HELCOM sub-basin level 2 delineation include Åland Sea and Archipelago Sea (AS), Bothnian Bay (BB), Bothnian Sea (BS), Gulf of Finland (GoF), Northern Baltic Proper (NBP), and the Quark (Q). Black lines demonstrate borders of HELCOM level 2 sub-basins and blue lines mark the EEZ borders between Finland, Sweden, Estonia and Russian Federation.

Appendix B. . Spearman correlation analyses for each sub-basin

Spearman correlation analysis results between NIS proportion and CBI for each open sea and coastal subbasin, as well as for all open sea and coastal samples with low NIS proportion (NIS proportion < 0,174) and high NIS proportion (NIS proportion \geq 0,174) (Fig. 7). Number of data points (n), Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ) and p -value were bolded when statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) were detected.

Sea area	n	ρ	p
Open sea areas			
GoF	677	-0.436	<0.001
AS	153	0.224	0.005
BS	673	0.78	<0.001
Q	185	0.261	<0.001
BB	575	0.673	<0.001
All open sea	2263	0.329	<0.001
Coastal sea areas			
GoF	4540	-0.219	<0.001
AS	2374	-0.001	0.971
BS	1096	0.104	0.001
Q	1117	0.154	<0.001
BB	1543	0.069	0.007
All coastal	10,672	-0.038	<0.001
NIS Low (NIS proportion < 0,174)			
All open sea	1530	0.365	<0.001
All coastal	4942	0.422	<0.001
All samples	6472	0.531	<0.001
NIS High (NIS proportion \geq 0,174)			
All open sea	733	-0.722	<0.001
All coastal	5730	-0.615	<0.001
All samples	6463	-0.629	<0.001

Appendix C. Spearman correlation analyses for each sub-basin

Correlation graphs between NIS proportion and CBI for all studied subbasins. Open sea graphs on the left, coastal graphs on the right.

References

- Ådjers, K., Appelberg, M., Eschbaum, R., Lappalainen, A., Minde, A., Repecka, R., Thoresson, G., 2006. Trends in coastal fish stocks of the Baltic Sea. *Boreal Environ. Res.* 11 (1), 13–25. <https://www.borenav.net/BER/archive/pdfs/ber11/ber11-013.pdf>.
- Bailey, S.A., Brown, L., Campbell, M.L., Canning-Clode, J., Carlton, J.T., Castro, N., Chainho, P., Chan, F.T., Creed, J.C., Curd, A., Darling, J., Fofonoff, P., Galil, B.S., Hewitt, C.L., Inglis, G.J., Keith, I., Mandrak, N.E., Marchini, A., McKenzie, C.H., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Ojaveer, H., Pires-Teixeira, L.M., Robinson, T.B., Ruiz, G.M., Seaward, K., Schwindt, E., Son, M.O., Therriault, T.W., Zhan, A., 2020. Trends in the detection of aquatic non-indigenous species across global marine, estuarine and freshwater ecosystems: A 50-year perspective. *Divers. Distrib.* 26 (12), 1780–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.13167>.
- Berezina, N.A., Gubelit, Y.I., Polyak, Y.M., Sharov, A.N., Kudryavtseva, V.A., Lubimtsev, V.A., Petukhov, V.A., Shigaeva, T.D., 2017. An integrated approach to the assessment of the eastern Gulf of Finland health: a case study of coastal habitats. *J. Marine Syst.* 171, 159–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2016.08.013>.
- Bertrand, Y., Pleijel, F., Rouse, G.W., 2006. Taxonomic surrogacy in biodiversity assessments, and the meaning of Linnaean ranks. *Syst. Biodivers.* 4 (2), 149–159. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1477200005001908>.
- AquaNIS Editorial Board, 2015. Information system on Aquatic Non-Indigenous and Cryptogenic Species. World Wide Web electronic publication. Version 2.36+. www.corpi.ku.lt/databases/aquanis (Accessed 11 August 2022).
- Bonsdorff, E., 2006. Zoobenthic diversity-gradients in the Baltic Sea: continuous post-glacial succession in a stressed ecosystem. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 330 (1), 383–391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2005.12.041>.
- Briski, E., Kotronaki, S.G., Cuthbert, R.N., Bortolus, A., Campbell, M.L., Dick, J.T., Fofonoff, P., Galil, B.S., Hewitt, C.L., Lockwood, J.L., MacIsaac, H.J., Ricciardi, A., Ruiz, G., Schwindt, E., Sommer, U., Zhan, A., Carlton, J.T., 2023. Does non-native diversity mirror Earth's biodiversity? *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13781>.
- Canada, T., 2021. Ballast water regulations, SOR/2021-120. Accessed 30 July 2023. <https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/regulations/SOR-2021-120/FullText.html>.
- Chase, J.M., Knight, T.M., 2013. Scale-dependent effect sizes of ecological drivers on biodiversity: why standardised sampling is not enough. *Ecol. Lett.* 16, 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12112>.
- Conley, D.J., Björck, S., Bonsdorff, E., Carstensen, J., Destouni, G., Gustafsson, B.G., Hietanen, S., Kortekaas, M., Kuosa, H., Markus Meier, H.E., Müller-Karulis, B., Nordberg, K., Norkko, A., Nürnberg, G., Pitkänen, H., Rabalais, N.N., Rosenberg, R., Savchuk, O.P., Slomp, C.P., Voss, M., Wulff, F., Zillén, L., 2009. Hypoxia-related processes in the Baltic Sea. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43 (10), 3412–3420. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es802762a>.
- Costello, M.J., Bouchet, P., Emblow, C.S., Legakis, A., 2006. European marine biodiversity inventory and taxonomic resources: state of the art and gaps in knowledge. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 316, 257–268. <https://www.int-res.com/articles/meps/oa/m316p257.pdf>.
- Costello, M.J., Dekeyser, S., Galil, B., Hutchings, P., Katsanevakis, S., Pagad, S., Robinson, T., Turon, X., Vandepitte, L., Vanhoorne, B. and Verfaillie, K., 2021. Introducing the World Register of Introduced Marine Species (WRiMS). *Manag. Biol. Invasions.* 12(4), 792–811. <https://doi.org/10.3391/mbi.2021.12.4.02>.
- Darling, J.A., Galil, B.S., Carvalho, G.R., Rius, M., Viard, F., Piraino, S., 2017. Recommendations for developing and applying genetic tools to assess and manage biological invasions in marine ecosystems. *Mar. Policy.* 85, 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.08.014>.
- Dinapoli, A., Klusmann-Kolb, A., 2010. The long way to diversity—phylogeny and evolution of the Heterobranchia (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* 55 (1), 60–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2009.09.019>.
- EC, 2008. Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive).
- EC, 2011. Our life insurance, our natural capital: an EU biodiversity strategy to 2020.

- EC, 2017. Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 laying down criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment. https://mcc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/ComDec/Com_dec_GES_2017_848_EU.pdf.
- EC, 2020. Bringing nature back into our lives; EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030.
- Eliason, A., Haahntela, L., 1969. *Polydora* (Boccardia) *redeki* Horst (Polychaeta, Spionidae) from Finland. *Ann. Zool. Fennici* 6 (3), 215–218. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23731375>.
- EPA, 2023. EPA Settles with Shipping Companies over Claims of Clean Water Act Violations. United States Environmental Protection Agency. <https://www.epa.gov/newsreleases/epa-settles-shipping-companies-over-claims-clean-water-act-violations> (Accessed 15 August 2023).
- Helcom, 2017. Manual for Marine Monitoring in the COMBINE programme of HELCOM. Accessed 20 May 2023 Online. <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Manual-for-Marine-Monitoring-in-the-COMBINE-Programme-of-HELCOM.pdf>.
- Helcom, 2022. HELCOM subbasins 2022 (level 2). Accessed 18 February 2023. <https://metadata.helcom.fi/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/d4b6296c-fd19-462c-94d2-4c81b9313d77>.
- HELCOM and OSPAR, 2020. HELCOM/OSPAR Joint Ballast Water Exemptions Decision Support Tool: https://maps.helcom.fi/website/RA_tool/ (Accessed 18 August 2023).
- HELCOM, 2018. Trends in arrival of new non-indigenous species. HELCOM core indicator report. <https://helcom.fi/media/core%20indicators/Trends-in-arrival-of-new-non-indigenous-species-HELCOM-core-indicator-2018.pdf> (Accessed 14 January 2023).
- HELCOM, 2021. HELCOM Monitoring programme for non-indigenous species: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Non-indigenous-species.pdf> (Accessed 2 August 2023).
- HELCOM, 2023b. HELCOM Thematic assessment of biodiversity 2016–2021. Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings No.191." Available at: https://helcom.fi/post_type_publications/holas3_bio (Accessed 28 July 2023).
- HELCOM, 2023a. HELCOM Thematic assessment of hazardous substances, marine litter, underwater noise and non-indigenous species 2016–2021. Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings n° 190. Available at: https://helcom.fi/post_type_publications/holas3_haz (Accessed 28 July 2023).
- Hietanen, S., Laine, A.O., Lukkari, K., 2007. The complex effects of the invasive polychaetes *Marenzelleria* spp. on benthic nutrient dynamics. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 352 (1), 89–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2007.07.018>.
- Holopainen, R., Lehtiniemi, M., Meier, H.E.M., Albertsson, J., Gorokhova, E., Kotta, J., Viitasalo, M., 2016. Impacts of changing climate on the non-indigenous invertebrates in the northern Baltic Sea by end of the twenty-first century. *Biol. Invasions* 18, 3015–3032. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1197-z>.
- Ieno, E.N., Solan, M., Batty, P., Pierce, G.J., 2006. How biodiversity affects ecosystem functioning: roles of infaunal species richness, identity and density in the marine benthos. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 311, 263–271. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24870050>.
- IMO, 2023a. Report of the Ballast Water Review Group. International Maritime Organization, London. MEPC 80/WP.13.
- IMO, 2023b. Report of the Working Group on Marine Biosafety. International Maritime Organization, London. PPR 10/WP.5.
- Jakobsson, M., Stranne, C., O'Regan, M., Greenwood, S.L., Gustafsson, B., Humborg, C., Weidner, E., 2019. Bathymetric properties of the Baltic Sea. *Ocean Sci* 15 (4), 905–924. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-905-2019>.
- Jensen, K.R., Andersen, P., Andersen, N.R., Bruhn, A., Buur, H., Carl, H., Jakobsen, H., Jaspers, C., Lundgreen, K., Nielsen, R., Strandberg, B., 2023. Reviewing introduction histories, pathways, invasiveness, and impact of non-indigenous species in danish marine waters. *Diversity* 15 (3), 434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15030434>.
- Jost, L., 2006. Entropy and diversity. *Oikos* 113 (2), 363–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2006.0030-1299.14714.x>.
- Karlson, A.M., Almqvist, G., Skóra, K.E., Appelberg, M., 2007. Indications of competition between non-indigenous goby and native flounder in the Baltic Sea. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* 64 (3), 479–486. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsl049>.
- Katsanevakis, S., Tempera, F., Teixeira, H., 2016. Mapping the impact of alien species on marine ecosystems: the Mediterranean Sea case study. *Divers. Distrib.* 22 (6), 694–707. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12429>.
- Kauppi, L., Norrko, A., Norrko, J., 2015. Large-scale species invasion into a low-diversity system: spatial and temporal distribution of the invasive polychaetes *Marenzelleria* spp. in the Baltic Sea. *Biol. Invasions* 17, 2055–2074. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-015-0860-0>.
- Klais, R., Lehtiniemi, M., Rubene, G., Semenov, A., Margonski, P., Ikauniece, A., Simm, M., Pöllumäe, A., Griniene, E., Mäkinen, K., Ojaveer, H., 2016. Spatial and temporal variability of zooplankton in a temperate semi-enclosed sea: implications for monitoring design and long-term studies. *J. Plankton Res.* 38 (3), 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbw022>.
- Kuhn, A.M., Dutkiewicz, S., Jahn, O., Clayton, S., Rynearson, T.A., Mazloff, M.R., Barton, A.D., 2019. Temporal and spatial scales of correlation in marine phytoplankton communities. *J. Geophys. Res. Oceans* 124 (12), 9417–9438. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015331>.
- Laine, A.O., Andersin, A.B., Leiniö, S., Zuur, A.F., 2007. Stratification-induced hypoxia as a structuring factor of macrozoobenthos in the open Gulf of Finland (Baltic Sea). *J. Sea Res.* 57 (1), 65–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2006.08.003>.
- Lehikoinen, A., Heikinheimo, O., Lehtonen, H., Rusanen, P., 2017. The role of cormorants, fishing effort and temperature on the catches per unit effort of fisheries in Finnish coastal areas. *Fish. Res.* 190, 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2017.02.008>.
- Lehtiniemi, M., Ojaveer, H., David, M., Galil, B., Gollasch, S., McKenzie, C., Minchin, D., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Olenin, S., Pederson, J., 2015. Dose of truth—monitoring marine non-indigenous species to serve legislative requirements. *Mar. Policy* 54, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.12.015>.
- Lehtiniemi, M., Outinen, O., Puntilla-Dodd, R., 2020. Citizen science provides added value in the monitoring for coastal non-indigenous species. *J. Environ. Manag.* 267, 110608 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110608>.
- Massé, C., Viard, F., Humbert, S., Antajan, E., Aubry, L., Bachelet, G., Bernard, G., Bouchet, V.M.P., Burel, T., Dauvin, J.-C., Delegrange, A., Derrien-Courtel, S., Droual, G., Goullieux, B., Gouilletquer, P., Guérin, L., Janson, A.-L., Jourde, J., Labruno, C., Lavesque, N., Leclerc, J.-C., Le Duff, M., Le Garrec, V., Noël, P., Nowaczyk, A., Pergent-Martini, C., Pezy, J.-P., Raoux, A., Raybaud, V., Ruitton, S., Sauriau, P.-G., Spilmont, N., Thibault, D., Vincent, D., Curd, A., 2023. An overview of marine non-indigenous species found in three contrasting biogeographic metropolitan french regions: insights on distribution. *Origins and Pathways of Introduction. Diversity* 15 (2), 161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15020161>.
- Mlambo, M.C., 2014. Not all traits are 'functional': insights from taxonomy and biodiversity-ecosystem functioning research. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 23, 781–790. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-014-0618-5>.
- Norling, K., Rosenberg, R., Hulth, S., Grémare, A., Bonsdorff, E., 2007. Importance of functional biodiversity and species-specific traits of benthic fauna for ecosystem functions in marine sediment. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 332, 11–23. <https://www.int-res.com/abstracts/meps/v332/p11-23/>.
- Nygård, H., Oinonen, S., Hällfors, H.A., Lehtiniemi, M., Rantajarvi, E., Uusitalo, L., 2016. Price vs. value of marine monitoring. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 3, 205. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00205>.
- Nygård, H., Lindegarth, M., Darr, A., Dinesen, G.E., Eigaard, O.R., Lips, I., 2020. Developing benthic monitoring programmes to support precise and representative status assessments: a case study from the Baltic Sea. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 192, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-020-08764-7>.
- Ojaveer, H., Galil, B.S., Minchin, D., Olenin, S., Amorim, A., Canning-Clode, J., Chainho, P., Copp, G.H., Gollasch, S., Jelmert, A., Lehtiniemi, M., McKenzie, C., Mikus, J., Miossec, L., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Pečarevič, M., Pederson, J., Quilez-Badia, G., Wijsman, J.W.M., Zenetos, A., 2014. Ten recommendations for advancing the assessment and management of non-indigenous species in marine ecosystems. *Mar. Policy* 44, 160–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2013.08.019>.
- Ojaveer, H., Galil, B.S., Carlton, J.T., Allevay, H., Gouilletquer, P., Lehtiniemi, M., Marchini, A., Miller, W., Occhipinti-Ambrogi, A., Peharda, M., Ruiz, G.M., Williams, S.L., Zaiko, A., 2018. Historical baselines in marine bioinvasions: implications for policy and management. *PLoS One* 13 (8), e0202383.
- Ojaveer, H., Kotta, J., Outinen, O., Einberg, H., Zaiko, A., Lehtiniemi, M., 2021. Meta-analysis on the ecological impacts of widely spread non-indigenous species in the Baltic Sea. *Sci. Total Environ.* 786, 147375 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147375>.
- Ojaveer, H., Lumberg, A., 1995. On the role of *Cercopagis* (*Cercopagis*) *pengoi* (Ostroumov) in Parnu Bay and the NE part of the Gulf of Riga ecosystem. *Proc. Estonian Acad. Sci. Ecol.* 5 (1/2), 20–25. <https://doi.org/10.3176/ecol.1995.1/2.03>.
- Ojaveer, H., Olenin, S., Naršcius, A., Florin, A.B., Ezhova, E., Gollasch, S., Jensen, K.R., Lehtiniemi, M., Minchin, D., Normant-Saremba, M., Strake, S., 2017. Dynamics of biological invasions and pathways over time: a case study of a temperate coastal sea. *Biol. Invasions* 19 (3), 799–813. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1316-x>.
- Olenin, S., Minchin, D., Daunys, D., 2007. Assessment of biopollution in aquatic ecosystems. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 55 (7–9), 379–394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2007.01.010>.
- Olenin, S., Naršcius, A., Gollasch, S., Lehtiniemi, M., Marchini, A., Minchin, D., Šrėbaliene, G., 2016. New arrivals: an indicator for non-indigenous species introductions at different geographical scales. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 3, 208. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00208>.
- Outinen, O., Forsström, T., Yli-Rosti, J., Vesakoski, O., Lehtiniemi, M., 2019. Monitoring of sessile and mobile epifauna—considerations for non-indigenous species. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 141, 332–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.02.055>.
- Outinen, O., Bailey, S.A., Broeg, K., Chasse, J., Clarke, S., Daigle, R.M., Gollasch, S., Kakkonen, J.E., Lehtiniemi, M., Normant-Saremba, M., Ogilvie, D., 2021. Exceptions and exemptions under the ballast water management convention—Sustainable alternatives for ballast water management? *J. Environ. Manag.* 293, 112823 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112823>.
- Png-Gonzalez, L., Comas-González, R., Calvo-Manazza, M., Follana-Berná, G., Ballesteros, E., Díaz-Tapia, P., Falcón, J.M., Raso, J.E.G., Gofas, S., González-Porto, M., López, E., Ramos-Esplá, A.A., Velasco, E., Carbonell, A., 2023. Updating the national baseline of non-indigenous species in spanish marine waters. *Diversity* 15 (5), 630. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d15050630>.
- Pollux, B.A.J., Velde, G. and Vaate, A., 2010. A perspective on global spread of *Dreissena polymorpha*: a review on possibilities and limitations. In Velde, G. van der; Rajagopal, S.; Vaate, A. bij de (ed.), *The zebra mussel in europe*, 45–58. Backhuys Publishers, Leiden/Weikersheim. <https://hdl.handle.net/2066/84350>.
- Rinne, H., Boström, M., Björklund, C., Sahla, M., 2021. Functionality of HELCOM HUB classification in describing variation in rocky shore communities of the northern Baltic Sea. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 249, 107044 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2020.107044>.
- Roswell, M., Dushoff, J., Winfree, R., 2021. A conceptual guide to measuring species diversity. *Oikos* 130 (3), 321–338. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.07202>.
- Ruban, G.I., 2020. History of baltic sea sturgeon fauna formation. *Russ. J. Biol. Invasions* 11, 372–378. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S207511172004013X>.
- Rudnick, D.A., Hieb, K., Grimmer, K.F., Resh, V.H., 2003. Patterns and processes of biological invasion: the Chinese mitten crab in San Francisco Bay. *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 4 (3), 249–262. <https://doi.org/10.1078/1439-1791-00152>.

- Ruiz, G.M., Carlton, J.T., Grosholz, E.D., Hines, A.H., 1997. Global invasions of marine and estuarine habitats by non-indigenous species: mechanisms, extent, and consequences. *Am. Zool.* 37 (6), 621–632. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/37.6.621>.
- Scriven, D.R., DiBacco, C., Locke, A., Therriault, T.W., 2015. Ballast water management in Canada: a historical perspective and implications for the future. *Mar. Policy.* 59, 121–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.05.014>.
- Simberloff, D., Gibbons, L., 2004. Now you see them, now you don't! – population crashes of established introduced species. *Biol. Invasions.* 6, 161–172. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:BINV.0000022133.49752.46>.
- Sjöqvist, C., Godhe, A., Jonsson, P.R., Sundqvist, L., Kremp, A., 2015. Local adaptation and oceanographic connectivity patterns explain genetic differentiation of a marine diatom across the North Sea-Baltic Sea salinity gradient. *Mol. Ecol.* 24 (11), 2871–2885. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13208>.
- Staehr, P.A., Jakobsen, H.H., Hansen, J.L., Andersen, P., Christensen, J., Göke, C., Thomsen, M.S., Stebbing, P.D., 2020. Trends in records and contribution of non-indigenous and cryptogenic species to marine communities in Danish waters: potential indicators for assessing impact. *Aquat. Invasions.* 15 (2), 217–244. <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2020.15.2.02>.
- Syke., 2020. *Seurantakäsikirja Suomen merenhoitosuunnitelman seurantaohjelmaan vuosille 2020–2026.* 47. ISSN 1796–1726 Report number.
- Tsiamis, K., Palialexis, A., Stefanova, K., Gladan, Ž.N., Skejić, S., Despalatović, M., Cvitković, I., Dragičević, B., Dulčić, J., Vidjak, O., Bojanić, N., 2019. Non-indigenous species refined national baseline inventories: a synthesis in the context of the European Union's Marine Strategy Framework Directive. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 145, 429–435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2019.06.012>.
- Tsiamis, K., Palialexis, A., Connor, D., Antoniadis, S., Bartilotti, C., Bartolo, G.A., Berggreen, U.C., Boschetti, S., Buschbaum, C., Canning-Clode, J., Carbonell, A., Castriota, L., Corbeau, C., Costa, A., Cvitković, I., Despalatović, M., Dragičević, B., Dulčić, J., Fortić, A., Francé, J., Gittenberger, A., Gizzi, F., Gollasch, S., Gruszka, P., Hegarty, M., Hema, T., Jensen, K., Josephides, M., Kabuta, S., Kerckhof, F., Kovtun-Kante, A., Krakau, M., Kraśniewski, W., Lackschewitz, D., Lehtiniemi, M., Lieberum, C., Linnamägi, M., Lipej, L., Livi, S., Lundgreen, K., Magliozzi, C., Massé, C., Mavrić, B., Michailidis, N., Moncheva, S., Mozetić, P., Naddafi, R., Ninčević, G.Z., Ojaveer, H., Olenin, S., Orlando-Bonaca, M., Ouerghi, A., Parente, M., Pavlova, P., Peterlin, M., Pitacco, V., Png-Gonzalez, L., Rousou, M., Sala-Pérez, M., Serrano, A., Skorupski, J., Smolders, S., Srebalienė, G., Stæhr, P.A., Stefanova, K., Strake, S., Tabarcea, C., Todorova, V., Trkov, D., Tuaty-Guerra, M., Vidjak, O., Zenetos, A., Žuljević, A., Cardoso, A.C., 2021. Marine Strategy Framework Directive-Descriptor 2, Non-Indigenous Species, Delivering solid recommendations for setting threshold values for non-indigenous species pressure on European seas, EUR 30640 EN. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- UNCTAD, 2021. *Review of Maritime Transport, 2021.* UNCTAD/RMT/2021. United Nations Publications, New York.
- UNEP, 1994. *Convention on biological diversity. Text and Annexes.* UNEP/CBD/94/1, Switzerland. <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/8340> (Accessed 29 July 2023).
- Zaiko, A., Lehtiniemi, M., Narščius, A., Olenin, S., 2011. Assessment of bioinvasion impacts on a regional scale: a comparative approach. *Biol. Invasions.* 13, 1739–1765. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-010-9928-z>.